

INVESTIGATION OF SUBCRITICAL CRACK GROWTH IN GLASS FIBERS USING LOAD RELAXATION TESTS ON BUNDLES

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1 General Introduction

Many inorganic fibers are sensitive to subcritical crack growth activated by environment. Failure occurs although the applied stress is much smaller than the fracture stress. This mechanism has been extensively investigated on ceramics, glasses and glass fibers, at room temperature essentially. It has been recently evidenced on SiC-based fibers at high temperatures. The present paper proposes a very powerful approach to static fatigue. It is based on tests performed on multifilament tows under deformation-controlled condition (load relaxation technique). This technique, which has not been used before, because of practical difficulties for deformation control during long-term tests, permits the application of identical constant stresses on all the fibers during a single test. Thus it provides a statistically significant rupture time database containing quite as many data as there are fibers in the tows.

Bundles about 2000 E-glass filaments were used in the present paper. The samples were immersed in water during the static fatigue tests. Crack velocity - stress intensity factor diagrams for single filaments were derived from experimental stress - rupture time data. A closed form expression for statistical distributions of fibre lifetimes was established. It was found to compare fairly well with the experimental results, which assessed the approach, and validated new findings.

2 Experimental

During each test, 2000 filaments were tested, which provides a significant database for statistical analysis of data.

A servo-pneumatic testing machine that had been designed and built in-house was used. It is equipped

with a 500 N load cell. Displacement control of the cross head for longterm tests is ensured through pneumatic cushions. Deformations were measured using a contact extensometer (with a ± 2.5 mm elongation displacement transducer) that was attached to the specimen.

Specimens were first impregnated with water.

3 Model

The subcritical crack growth model is based on the simple power form of crack velocity versus stress intensity factor, which is usually employed to describe the slow propagation of cracks caused by environment under load in ceramics and glass materials:

$$V = \frac{da}{dt} = V^* \left(\frac{K_I}{K_{IC}} \right)^n \quad (1)$$

where V is crack velocity, a is crack length, t is time, K_I is the stress intensity factor, K_{IC} is the critical stress intensity factor, V^* and n are constants depending respectively on environment and material.

The lifetime of a single fiber under constant stress is given by equation (2):

$$t = \frac{2K_{IC}^2}{V^* Y^2 \sigma^2 (n-2)} \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_f}{\sigma} \right)^{n-2} - 1 \right] \quad (2)$$

The reference strength of each fiber σ_f can be calculated using the well-known Weibull equation of distribution of failure stresses measured in inert environment:

$$P = 1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{v}{v_0}\right)\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0}\right)^m\right] \quad (3)$$

Then, the statistical distribution of single filaments rupture times is given by equation (4):

$$P(t, \sigma, v) = 1 - \exp\left[-\left(\frac{v}{v_0}\right)\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0}\right)^m \left(1 + \frac{t}{t^*} \frac{n-2}{2}\right)^{\frac{m}{n-2}}\right] \quad (4)$$

where $P(t, \sigma, v)$ is the failure probability at time t , under stress σ , for a fiber with volume v . t^* is a

stress dependent scale factor: $t^* = \frac{K_{IC}^2}{V^* \sigma^2 Y^2}$.

This equation is important for lifetime predictions and establishing Strength/Probability/Time diagrams.

4 Results

Load relaxation follows a power law, with n as force exponent. The slow crack growth constants were extracted from the load relaxation curve. The crack propagation diagrams $V(K_I/K_{IC})$ were found to consist of two distinct curves characterized by ($n \approx 30$, $V^* \approx 10^{-6}$ m/s) and ($n \approx 12$, $V^* \approx 10^{-9}$ m/s). This unusual diagram results from the presence of two families of fibers: a family of weak fibers with short life, and a family of strong fibers with long life. The family of weak fibers was present only under small deformations. The family of strong fibers was found to dominate under larger deformations ($\epsilon > 0.8\%$, $\sigma > 600$ MPa).

Figure 1 shows that predictions are in excellent agreement with experimental data, when both populations of fibers are taken into account. This definitely validates the model, as well as the hypothesis on the presence of two families of fibers in the bundles. Figure 2 also shows that predictions with $n = 12$ are satisfactory when the weak fibers have not been completely eliminated. Equation (4) can be used to establish the stress-probability-time diagrams.

5 Conclusions

It was shown that the life of each fiber in a bundle is commensurate with the fiber reference strength (equation (2)). Then, it was shown that the rank of each failing fiber could be derived from relaxation of the load on bundle, so that the reference strength of each ailing fiber is no longer an unknown. This is an important result that is worth pointing out. Stress-failure time relations were established, as well as the equation of rupture time distribution. This latter equation depends on stressed volume, time and applied stress. It can be used for lifetime predictions, as well as for establishing stress-probability-time diagrams.

Figure 1: Statistical distributions of lifetimes predicted using equation (4) and comparison with experimental results.